

Bioperspectives for Shape-Memory Polymers as Shape Programmable, Active Materials

Andreas Lendlein,^{*,†,‡} Maria Balk,[†] Natalia A. Tarazona,[†] and Oliver E. C. Gould[†]

[†]Institute of Biomaterial Science, Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht, Kantstrasse 55, Teltow, Germany

[‡]Institute of Chemistry, University of Potsdam, Karl-Liebknecht-Straße 24-25, Potsdam, Germany

ABSTRACT: Within the natural world, organisms use information stored in their material structure to generate a physical response to a wide variety of environmental changes. The ability to program synthetic materials to intrinsically respond to environmental changes in a similar manner has the potential to revolutionize material science. By designing polymeric devices capable of responsively changing shape or behavior based on information encoded into their structure, we can create functional physical behavior, including a shape-memory and an actuation capability. Here we highlight the stimuli-responsiveness and shape-changing ability of biological materials and biopolymer-based materials, plus their potential biomedical application, providing a bioperspective on shape-memory materials. We address strategies to incorporate a shape-memory (actuation) function in polymeric materials, conceptualized in terms of its relationship with inputs (environmental stimuli) and outputs (shape change). Challenges and opportunities associated with the integration of several functions in a single material body to achieve multifunctionality are discussed. Finally, we describe how elements that sense, convert, and transmit stimuli have been used to create multisensitive materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing urgency of global challenges in healthcare, energy, and the environment have propelled smart materials to the forefront of international scientific research, with the aim of providing devices that can improve quality of life. Programmable polymeric materials can encode physical information into their structure and, subsequently, use that information to respond and adapt to environmental changes. Within this group, shape-memory polymers (SMPs) are highly deformable materials that can be programmed to recover a memorized shape in response to a variety of environmental and spatially localized stimuli.¹ Their ability to generate diverse physical movement, such as bending, twisting, or contraction, has led to their application as micromachines, artificial muscles, morphing medical devices, and others.² However, the geometric complexity of movement realized for synthetic materials still falls short of the vast array of shape-changing behavior realized in the natural world. The ability of plants, for example, to complement and enhance other functionality using directed movement is especially impressive.

In a classical thermoplastic material, schematically illustrated in Figure 1a, the phase transition of a structural unit within the polymer matrix enables the reshaping of the material into an alternative form by melting and reprocessing. The lack of chemical cross-linking within the material means that the two forms, before and after deformation, have no significant difference in entropy. Here, melting is associated with a complete loss of structural information and shape. The

incorporation of dynamic covalent bonds, as schematically illustrated in Figure 1b, also allows for shape reconfiguration. Shape reconfiguration is achieved by the breaking and forming of bonds between adjacent polymer chains and provides mechanical integrity to the two formed shapes. The exchange kinetics of the dynamic covalent bonding and subsequent rearrangement of polymer chains within the network, prevent the accumulation of entropic energy and the persistence of structural information within the material upon reshaping. In a shape-memory material, as schematically illustrated in Figure 1c, additional permanent covalent cross-links are added to provide mechanical stability during deformation of the material. The combination of this covalent cross-linking with a structural unit capable of providing additional reversible netpoints to the polymer matrix allows for the storage of structural information during reshaping. This structural unit can take the form of dynamic covalent bonds (as shown in Figure 1c(ii)) or a domain capable of undergoing a thermally responsive phase transition (as shown in Figure 1c(i)). This reshaping process, named programming, generates an entropy difference between the initial and programmed forms. Netpoints formed by physical or dynamic covalent cross-linking are then used to “fix” the programmed shape while retaining structural information about the previous form of the

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Figure 1. Schematic illustration depicting the structural composition of (a) a classical thermoplastic material with crystalline domains (blue), (b) networks containing dynamic covalent bonding (green), (c) reprogrammable shape-memory materials with (i) crystalline netpoints (orange) and (ii) dynamic covalent bonding (green) and permanent cross-links (black).

material. This retention of structural information within the material has been termed shape-memory.¹

Recent work has demonstrated that a shape-memory effect (SME) can also be designed to enable a reversible actuation by utilizing orientated crystallization to reform the postprogramming low entropy state.³ In this Perspective, we address the versatility of shape programmable materials that used encoded physical information to perform a one-way movement (as output of a SME) and a controlled reversible actuation capability. We describe the recent progress made in this class of smart polymeric materials and emphasize the key differences between the two shape programmable functionalities in terms of the input–function–output relationship.

SMPs that respond to external stimuli (as an input signal) have many similarities with nature, since most biomolecules

are intrinsically capable of noticing alternations in their local environment.⁴ In contrast to conventional SMPs, shape deformations in biological systems such as plants are programmed at the microstructural level, relying, for example, on the orientation and degree of alignment of cellulose microfibrils within the plant cell walls.⁵ We present one-way movements and controlled reversible actuation effects realized by plants, wool, and silk, as well as biopolymer-based SMPs, providing a bioperspective on the development of shape-memory materials.

The aim of the next generation of smart devices for health technologies is to combine the SME with other attractive functionalities, such as biodegradability, self-healing, or drug release capability.^{6,7} This multifunctionality is achieved through a prudent combination of different functional capabilities, where each function supplies a particular physical or chemical process for system-level improvements beyond the status quo.⁸ The implementation of such functions in man-made biomaterials has been achieved by tailoring their molecular structure, phase morphology, device geometry, or by designing hybrid and functionalized materials to obtain morphologies and functionalities more related to the desired application. These functions should be integrated in a material and should be present under relevant conditions, for instance during the interaction with biological systems. Ideally they should also meet site-specific and organ-specific requirements. Advances in this area are directed toward the design of multifunctional biomaterials with (i) orthogonal functions that are independently localized within a single complex body or (ii) sequentially couple functions that enable linking functions according to a domino effect.^{9,10} Here, we will show the advantages and challenges of accommodating different and potentially interfering functions and how sophisticated component assemblies are required to perform this task. Further, in this Perspective we examine the understanding of the input–function–output workflow to obtain deeper insights into design criteria for the next generation of multifunctional materials. A variety of possible environmental signals or stimuli will be elucidated, including thermal, photo, pH, electrical, chemical, and ionic. We highlight the protocols used to integrate elements that sense, convert, and transmit these stimuli to generate multisensitive materials.^{11,12} Finally, we discuss the usability of (multi)functional shape shifters and actuators in real world applications and conclude with some promising future directions for this research area.

2. SHAPE-PROGRAMMABLE MATERIALS: SHAPE-MEMORY EFFECT

Materials capable of intrinsic shape change can be separated into those that directly respond to external stimulation and those that translate environmental changes into geometric movement based on information physically programmed into their structure. In the latter case, the resulting function of the material, in combination with the polymer architecture, is denominated as a SME, and enables directed and on demand changes of the macroscopic appearance (Figure 2a). Here, the input (denominated as stimulus) is only an inducing environmental signal that causes removal of the internal structural barrier, initiating the recovery of the original shape. Stimuli can originate from a range of external sources, including temperature, light, magnetic or electric fields, enzymes, changes in pH value, or ion concentrations. The output is the SME, which can generate (multiple) shape shifts

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of directed movements in polymeric materials and plants. (a) Shape-memory function and an example of multiple shape shifts in hydrogels induced by changes in temperature.¹⁷ (b) Seedpod opening of *Impatiens glandulifera* as a representative example for an irreversible directed movement of plants.¹⁸ (c) Shape-memory actuation capability with the example of an origami flower, which enabled a reversible movement of the petals when cyclic changes in temperature are applied.²² (d) Closure of the leaves of *Dionaea muscipula Ellis*.²³ Panel that includes the shape-memory hydrogel is adapted with permission from ref 17 under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>). Copyright 2019 IOP Publishing Ltd. Panel including the seedpod opening is adapted with permission from ref 18. Copyright 2012 National Academy of Science. Panel including the origami flower is adapted with permission from ref 22. Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society. Panel including *Dionaea muscipula Ellis* reprinted with permission from ref 23. Copyright 2007 Taylor & Francis Ltd. (<http://www.tandfonline.com>).

by means of a dual-, triple-, quadruple-, or temperature-memory effect.^{13,14}

Motions between macroscopic shapes have been widely reported in water swollen polymeric materials (denominated as hydrogels).^{15,16} Within these materials there is an ongoing demand for an increase in the number of shape shifts for applications where complex macroscopic movements are required. For highly water swollen systems, the state of aggregation of water (transition from the solid to the liquid state at 0 °C and the transition from the liquid to the gaseous state at 100 °C) presents a limitation for the temperature range used as an input for shape shifting. The record for multiple shape-shifts by a hydrogel is four different shapes, one original shape plus three shape-shifts. (Figure 2a).¹⁷ The programming of this quadruple-shape function included three switching segments that generated reversible temporary cross-links, enabling the fixation of a deformed temporary shape. The initiation of the shape recovery was realized by increasing the temperature of water, with each switching segments independently addressed as they respond to different temperatures in the range from 5 to 90 °C. Based on the same principle depicted in Figure 2a, and aimed at applications in biomedicine, a smart valve that varies the flow of water with changes in temperature was fabricated. Such a valve was designed with two orifices that allowed a triple-shape effect (one original shape plus two shape-shifts) when heated and cooled between 25 and 80 °C.¹⁶ Although these shape shifts are one-way movements (irreversible), the introduction of new geometric information to reverse a transformation in shape could be possible by reprogramming steps via thermomechanical treatment.

Programmed deformations are widespread in natural systems, far from being completely understood, and serve as inspiration for the development of shape-changing biopolymers. Instead of molecular phase transition or combinations of different materials, plant movements rely on, for example, differences in tissue resistance to osmotic pressure (explosion movements for the distribution of spores and seeds), or controlled orientation and spatial distribution of cellulose microfibrils that restrict swelling or growth in certain directions, promoting organized, macroscopic self-shaping (reversible opening and closing movements).⁵ Figure 2b, shows the fracture of seedpods in *Impatiens glandulifera*, one of the fastest movements in the plant kingdom, as an example of a nonreversible directed movement.¹⁸ Here, the stored elastic energy in the pods is rapidly released upon fracture, with a new surface geometry of the plant component created, as the released energy is converted into the kinetic energy of the seeds. Explosive dehiscence as strategy to release seeds is initiated by mechanical stress (e.g., contact) as an inducing environmental effect, and the resulting macroscopic shape shift can be obtained within less than 3 μ s.¹⁹

In *Cardamine hirsuta*, the explosive mechanism to disperse seeds has been identified as a result of morphomechanical innovations at different spatial scales, where asymmetric lignin deposition in cell walls plays an important role.²⁰ Based on these principles, lignin has been incorporated in polymer networks to achieve inhomogeneity, resulting in, for example, triple SME.²¹ However, generating rapid motion in SMPs will require incorporating components based on spatial modulation that respond at different scales, enabling, for instance, the gradual storage of elastic energy, but the ability to release it rapidly, as seen in plants.

3. SHAPE-PROGRAMMABLE MATERIALS: SHAPE-MEMORY ACTUATION CAPABILITY

A traditional SME can be also implemented as a reversible effect enabling actuation behavior (Figure 2c). This evolution in programmable materials opened new alternatives to enable macroscopic and directed bidirectional movement for large numbers of cycles. This process is reliant on generating network anisotropy using a skeleton structure of geometry-determining crystallites in the material.¹ In shape-memory polymer actuators (SMPAs), the initiation of the macroscopic movement is not driven by an inductive stimulus, as presented for the shape-memory function; instead, the applied input signal directly controls the material output. Furthermore, the kinetics of the stimulus will greatly affect the kinetics of the function. A shape-memory actuation effect is illustrated in Figure 2c with the example of an origami flower based on two biocompatible semicrystalline polymers providing different melting transitions. Here, the reversible movement of five petals was obtained as a function of temperature.²² A more complex motion in such actuator systems was demonstrated by manufacturing a Manikin with a twisted actuator polymer that functioned as an arm. Remarkably, the actuator was able to perform a discontinuous and reversible movement of a traffic sign arrow that was coupled to the arm.²⁴

Comparable reversible shape transformations on the macroscopic level, triggered by a diversity of stimuli, can also be observed in autonomous reacting plants. *Dionaea muscipula Ellis* (Venus flytrap) is a very prominent demonstrator of this actuation capability²³ and, unsurprisingly, was pronounced by Darwin as one of the most wonderful plants in the world.²⁵ The closure of the Venus flytrap leaf can be initiated by a mechanical stimulation of the trigger hairs on the surface of the leaf, which generates a response within 100 ms (Figure 2d). This snap together of the leaves is only activated when two consecutive stimulations are applied by an insect within a short time period. The mechanism of this response relies on the combination of a rapid loss of turgor pressure²⁶ and a snap-buckling instability.²⁷ The reversible movement from the closed state to the opened state of the Venus flytrap was identified to include four reopening stages based on morphological changes.^{28,29}

4. FUNCTION–FUNCTION RELATIONSHIP IN MULTIFUNCTIONAL MATERIALS

Designing multifunctional materials based on SMPs requires a deep understanding of the structure–property–function interdependencies, which control the final efficacy of the devices.⁶ The final aim is to manufacture hierarchical structures in which the properties of the whole are greater than the sum of the parts. The main relations described in polymer materials are structure–properties, structure–function, process parameter–function, and function–function, the former being especially relevant in multifunctional materials and, therefore, the focus of this Perspective. A clear demonstration of the structure–property correlation has been shown in several studies where the thermal properties of a material are affected to a certain degree by the chain length of the integrated oligomers/polymers. In case of the widely used polyester segment poly(ϵ -caprolactone), the domains formed by dimers of ϵ -caprolactone (CL) are completely amorphous, the tetramer-based domains exhibit a T_m of -20 °C, and the thermal transition can be increased up to 60 – 64 °C for

polymer segments of CL with a molecular weight above 15,000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.^{30,31} The second, equally important, relationship in multifunctional materials is the structure–function relationship. The switching temperature (T_{sw} , temperature of highest rate of shape transformation) can correlate to the thermal properties resulting in increasing T_{sw} when the chain length of the included semicrystalline polymers (acting as switching segments) is increased.^{32,33} An example of the process parameter–function relationship can be observed during a thermomechanical treatment of a polymeric device, in which the temperature where a deformation was applied will be recognized by the material system. For this so-called temperature-memory effect, the adaption of T_{sw} is enabled.³⁴ The utilized polymers often exhibit a broad thermal transition. In this case, an overlap of both melting transitions associated with the semicrystalline polymers was apparent when the thermal properties were investigated. Hence, a systematic control of T_{sw} in the range from 32 to 65 °C could be demonstrated.³⁵

An exceptional attribute of multifunctional materials is the opportunity to integrate several functions while carefully designing the function–function relation on demand. There are essentially two relationships that can be targeted: orthogonal functions that are almost independent from each other and mandatorily require timely adapted steps or sequentially coupled functions that enable linking functions according to a domino effect.^{2,36–38} As schematically presented in Figure 3, the design of a triple functional polymer network

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of orthogonal functions and sequentially coupled functions in multifunctional materials.

system based on orthogonal functions have been successfully presented, where a shape-memory function (function 1) independent from the diffusion-controlled release (function 2) and biodegradation (function 3) was enabled.³⁶ The combination of these three effects could be expanded for the design of, for example, mechanically and pharmacologically active implants. The working mechanism was designed as follows: the shape-memory function is triggered by an increase in temperature, for instance, body temperature, allowing the material to self-anchor at a specific location; once the place of request is reached, the polymer structure allows the diffusion-controlled drug release that is chronologically followed by hydrolytic degradation. Remarkably, *in vitro* tests with this

material showed that the shape-shifting capability was not influenced by the presence of drugs, biodegradation did not affect the shape transformation or the diffusion-controlled release, and the drug release was not manipulated by the self-anchoring process. Hence, independent material functionalities (SME, drug release, degradation) are thereby crucial for utilizing the overall potential of the reported material system, which was addressed by realizing timely separated material functions.

Two of the major challenges for the independency between orthogonal functions are (i) to implement functions within a single complex body and (ii) to ensure that introducing a new functionality does not erase the ones that have previously been established.⁶ The potential of separated multifunctionalities is gaining increasing attention but still requires additional insight into allowing movement from classical fused-functionalities at the macroscale, toward highly integrated systems in which sensing, additive, and subtractive processes are possible. Research in this area envisions the integration of material science, computer science, and other related disciplines to model and simulate materials properties/performance and to manufacture “computing materials” or “robotic materials” that are able to function autonomously. These materials could combine different mechanisms with sensing and control, resolving by itself if the desired functions can be coupled or not.³⁹

Alternatively, sequentially coupled functions facilitate linking functions according to a domino-effect (Figure 3, section sequentially coupled functions). To explore this design, a SMP tube filled with protein factors was built by linking shape switching (function 1) and on-demand drug release (function 2).¹⁰ The design could be metaphorically compared to a confetti cannon, which uses nitrogen stored in a cylinder sealed with an outer case to produce energy and propel the confetti out of the cannon. The release of the nitrogen is achieved by turning a catch that undoes the stopper that keeps the nitrogen in place. In a similar way, the system proposed has three components: a tube-like container with shape-memory capability, a thermosensitive hydrogel (gelation at 33 °C, i.e., below body temperature) that acts as the nitrogen of the cannon, and a coating to seal the openings of the tube for payload protection and delayed release. Instead of a mechanical force, the system is triggered by near-infrared (NIR) that heats the polymer via a photothermal effect, inducing the shrinking of the SMP tube, a viscosity reduction of the hydrogel, and eventually drug release.¹⁰ Such systems are promising in the field of controlled release, since prominent challenges are addressed, including the susceptibility to enzymatic degradation, short circulation half-lives, and poor membrane permeability of therapeutic proteins to targeted disease sites.⁴⁰ Nonetheless, it is crucial to ensure that the output of the first function is compatible with the input of the second one. The use of sophisticated sequentially coupled functions, can be observed in the seed release mechanisms of a variety of plants. For instance, the buildup of elastic energy for seed disposal in *C. hirsuta* was described as the following sequence of events: a change in cell wall anisotropy following cellulose microfibrils reorientation, coupled with tension in the direction of the fruit width, causing exocarp cell growth to switch from the length to the width direction. This reorientation drives a change in exocarp cell shape from rectangular to square. Subsequent anisotropic deformation of these cells results in their shortening, causing tension to rapidly

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of different principles to include sensors in a shape-memory material. (a) Crystalline domains acting as a direct sensor, which respond to heat as stimulus. (b) Example of a signal converter as a sensor. Magnetic nanoparticles convert a magnetic field energy into heat energy. The resulting thermal effect induces the melting of crystalline domains. (c) An interconnected macroporous structure acts as a signal transmitter. Mechanical energy from ultrasound is amplified by the formation of cavitation bubbles. According to the porous morphology, gas bubbles are able to penetrate the material system. Once gas bubbles collapse, the generated mechanical force causes a mechanosensitive reorganization of rhodium–phosphine coordination bonds.

establish along the length of the valve. This tension is harnessed to drive curvature by coincident stiffening of the endocarp b layer, necessary for the explosive pod shatter.²⁰ The realization of a similar reorientation mechanism in SMPs has the potential to introduce new shapes and, therefore, inputs for coupling functions.

5. SENSING THE ENVIRONMENT

Key developments in the design of multifunctional materials enable the integration of several functions, in addition to the SME, by including sensors that respond to different stimuli. There are three different principles to achieve such a combination. For classical shape-memory materials, the chemical integration of photosensitive or thermosensitive units (direct sensors) into a multiblock copolymer permits a SME induced by a direct stimulus (Figure 4a). Thermally induced SMPs are among the most common shape programmable materials, and many reported studies rely on this

mechanism.^{3,41,42} These materials have the capability of returning from a temporary shape to their permanent shape when increasing the temperature, as presented in section 2 of this Perspective. Light has been widely utilized as a trigger/input in shape-programmable functions because of its distinct features as compared to direct heating. Among the advantages of using light are that (i) remote activation is feasible since light can travel long distances; (ii) the light beam (usually a laser) can be delivered to selected areas, allowing spatially controlled activation; and (iii) light-triggered processes can be suspended and resumed “on-demand” by turning off or turning on the excitation light.⁴³ Chemically integrated photochromic moieties (cinnamic groups) in the structure of a shape-memory film enabled reversible photo-cross-linking induced by ultraviolet light (UV) illumination to control the permanent shape and the recovery process.⁴⁴ Here, a film was stretched to 20% elongation by external stress, and both sides of the film were evenly irradiated with UV light ($\lambda > 260$ nm, for 60 min).

Once the external stress was released, the film maintained the elongated form. Irradiating the elongated shape with UV light of $\lambda < 260$ nm for 60 min induced cleaving of newly formed photosensitive cross-links, and the recovery of the memorized, permanent shape was observed.⁴⁴

The second principle for the integration of sensors within functions is based on the incorporation of a signal converter that translates a form of energy into another form, conventionally, thermal energy. A successful multifunctional system based on converters has been reported using NIR light⁴⁵ and an alternating magnetic field⁴⁶ as the induction signals. In these cases, the converters should be not only a strong light absorber, but also provide high efficiency in converting electromagnetic radiation into heat, leading to a photothermal-induced SME.^{10,45} For instance, graphene oxide (GOs) was used to fabricate poly(acrylic acid) (PAA)-grafted GO nanosheets (denoted as PAA-GO) within a poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) matrix (PVA/PAA-GO composites), enabling the triggering of shape recovery of the films by NIR light.⁴⁵ The film was elongated at 74 °C and cooled down to room temperature to fix the temporary shape. Under irradiation by a NIR laser, the temperature within the material system rapidly increased to 75.4 °C in 5 s, whereby a completely recovered shape could be achieved after 35 s. It was further demonstrated that films with large dimensions and complicated structures can also be triggered with NIR light for efficient shape recovery. Two pieces of petal-shaped PVA/PAA-GO films were assembled into an open flower as its permanent shape. The temporary shape was thermally fixed according to the described procedure. Under NIR light irradiation, the bud bloomed within 1 min to return to its permanent shape.⁴⁵

Noncontact triggering has also been achieved by magnetically induced shape-memory composites via a photothermal effect.^{46,47} As shown in Figure 4b, magnetic nanoparticles consisting, for example, of an iron(III) oxide core were incorporated in a thermoplastic SMP. In this example, the application of an alternating magnetic field induced inductive heating within the composite material resulting in a shape shift. In addition, also electrical conductive systems based on shape-memory materials were reported, including, for example, a gallium core⁴⁸ or carbon nanofibers.⁴⁹ Here, the application of an electrical field can be used to generate heat.

The third alternative to inserting sensors into multifunctional materials consists of the incorporation of transmitters. A transmitter senses a signal, converts it into an analog one, amplifying the signal, and finally transmits it from one place to another. This principle was used to create a polymeric system in which shape changes could be induced by ultrasonic cavitation-based mechanical force (CMF).⁵⁰ The key features of this “architected shape-memory function integration” were the interconnected macroporous structure with thin pore walls and the integration of rhodium–phosphine coordination bonds (Rh–P–CBs) acting as molecular switches. The SME was generated by the combination of the microphase morphology and the reversible dissociation of the Rh–P–CBs by a combination of CMF and low frequency ultrasound (Figure 4c). In this system, the mechanical energy from the ultrasound is generated by a cavitation process, as the rapid expansion and implosion of bubbles takes place in the media. Once the critical size of the gas bubbles is reached, their collapse generates a strong mechanical force that causes a mechanosensitive reorganization of the material topology by dissociation of Rh–P–CBs and acceleration of the ligand

exchange rate. The collapse of the bubbles inside the polymeric structure was only possible because of the porous morphology, which increased the surface area of the material and, subsequently, amplified the effect of the mechanical force generated by cavitation. Finally, the mechanically induced reorganization of the polymer skeleton caused the SME. Multifunctional materials based on this principle could be interesting candidates as mechanosensors or ultrasound controlled switches, which would have applications in specific environments (e.g., constant ambient or lower temperature, light avoiding).⁵⁰

These three fundamental principles (sensor, converter, and transmitter) are inspiring the design of advanced multifunctional materials, in which a diverse range of other stimuli are integrated. For example, a recently reported polymeric material capable of an enzymatic response has great promise for applications in controlled delivery modulated by the physiological status of cells/organs.⁵¹

6. SENSING THE ENVIRONMENT: THE PLANT KINGDOM

Movements in the natural world are used to enable important features like reproduction, defense against enemies, or nutrition.^{52,53} Visible changes in position or shape typically can be very slow (within minutes, hours, days, weeks), such as growth/climbing motion, or can be very fast (within milliseconds), exemplified by the spore discharge among fungi.^{54–56} While the macroscopic movement in plants possesses analogies to designed polymeric systems, the motion is based on a completely different and complex mechanism. Plant motion typically involves nastic movements or tropism.

Similar to polymeric materials, where the macroscopic shape shift will be triggered by an external stimulus, in nastic plant movements, the shape transformation can be induced by an environmental signal and will be guided by the characteristics (e.g., architecture) of the reacting plant organ.⁵⁷ Furthermore, this motion refers to a direction-independent movement, as described for the spore discharge among fungi (irreversible movement) and for the Venus flytrap (reversible motion). In the latter case, the trap close does not depend on where and in what direction the trigger hairs on the surface of the leaf are touched.⁵⁸ Another example for such a reversible touch-sensitive motion (denominated as thigmonastic movement) are *Mimosa* species such as *Mimosa pudica*, which are able to respond to a mechanical stimulus resulting in the folding up of its leaf (Figure 5, section nastic motion).⁵⁹ This nastic phenomenon is based on very fast changes in volume and shape within motor cells according to variations in cell turgor. Besides mechanical stimulation, the plant kingdom is also capable of nastic motions induced, for example, by temperature (thermonasty), light (photonasty), chemicals/nutrients (chemonasty), or water (hydronasty). The ability of *Tulipa iliensis* to respond to environmental temperature is illustrated in Figure 6.⁶⁰ The closure of this plant enables the maintenance of temperature within the flower, providing a stable micro-environment and promoting pollen germination. The nastic motion in pine cones from *Picea abies* is another example of a stimuli-sensitive and reversible behavior in plants, and can be obtained by changes in the environmental humidity.⁶¹ This hydronastic phenomenon relies on a bilayered structure within the cone, enabling a macroscopic shape shift from a tightly packed cone to an opened shape when humidity decreases.

Nastic motion

Tropicistic motion

Figure 5. Nastic and tropistic movements in plants. Nastic motion within the plant kingdom with the examples of touch-sensitivity in *Mimosa pudica*,⁵⁹ temperature-sensitivity, as demonstrated by *Tulip iliensis*,⁶⁰ and the hydronastic behavior of *Picea abies*.⁶¹ Tropicistic movements generated by plants via heliotropism with the example of *Helianthus annuus*,⁶² thigmotropic sensitivity of *Parthenocissus tricuspidata* tendrils,⁶³ gravitropic behavior illustrated by *Arabidopsis thaliana*,⁶⁴ and electropism with the example of pollen tubes from *Tulipa gesneriana*.⁶⁵ Panel including *Mimosa pudica* is reprinted with permission from ref 59. Copyright 2011 Taylor & Francis Ltd. (<http://www.tandfonline.com>). Panel including *Tulip iliensis* is adapted with permission from ref 60. Copyright 2013 Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences, John Wiley & Sons. Panel including *Picea abies* is adapted with permission from ref 61. Copyright 2009 The Royal Society, permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. Panel including *Helianthus annuus* is adapted with permission from ref 62. Copyright 2016 AAAS. Panel including *Parthenocissus tricuspidata* tendrils is reprinted with permission from ref 63. Copyright 2009 Elsevier. Panel including *Arabidopsis thaliana* is adapted with permission from ref 64. Copyright 2005 National Academy of Sciences, U.S.A. Panel including pollen

Figure 5. continued

tubes from *Tulipa gesneriana* is reprinted by permission from ref 65. Copyright 1991 Springer-Verlag (<https://link.springer.com/journal/497>).

When the motion is initiated by an environmental stimulus and, additionally, is determined by the direction of the signal, the movement of the plant is denominated as a tropistic movement. A classical example for this tropism is the heliotropic and reversible shape shift toward light of the sunflower *Helianthus annuus*. In Figure 5 (section tropistic motion), the nighttime reorientation of the sunflower stem is presented.⁶² This solar tracking movement is driven by antiphasic patterns of elongation on the east and west sides of the stem. Therefore, the plant is able to align their photosynthetic organ with the direction of the incoming sun light. The sunflower also exhibits a reorientation during the night, whereby the leaves and apices are directed to the east before the sun is rising. Furthermore, tropistic plant motion can also be observed in tendrils. As demonstrated in Figure 5, *Parthenocissus tricuspidata* tendrils are able to create attachment pads after touching with an object acting as a supporter, whereby climbing of the plant is enabled.⁶³ As the attachment depends on where and how the tendrils are touched, this movement can be denominated as an irreversible thigmotropic plant movement. Gravitropism presents another kind of stimulated motion (Figure 5, example of *Arabidopsis thaliana*), where plants provide the ability to reorient themselves based on the local gravitational field.⁶⁴ The specific response pathway (e.g., when horizontal gravistimulation is applied) involves the recognition of the gravitational field, the transduction into a physiological signal, and the transmission to the site of response, as well as a curvature-response, allowing the plant organ to resume growth. In addition, certain fields display electrosensitivity. As presented in Figure 5, the pollen tubes of *Tulipa gesneriana* are influenced by electrical stimulation, resulting in growth toward a negative electrode.⁶⁵

These examples of nastic and tropistic plant motions demonstrate the variety of macroscopic reversible and irreversible shape transformations within the plant kingdom. As these kinds of macroscopic movements illustrate key similarities to shape shifting and actuation materials on the macroscopic level, we believe that the exciting world of plants with its diversity in motions will be an inspiration for engineering artificial functional materials.

7. SHAPE-PROGRAMMABLE BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS AND BIOPOLYMER-BASED HYBRIDS

The responses of biological materials to stimuli provide organisms with various functions, such as mechanical protection and support, camouflage, and metabolism, as well as mechanosensing and actuation.⁶⁶ In general, organisms have to cope with a multitude of environmental constraints; therefore, biological materials intrinsically possess a nonlinear response to external stimuli.⁶⁷

Recently, the shape-memory behavior in keratin-based natural materials in response to water, specifically in feathers⁶⁸ and hair⁶⁹ has been reported. Although the shape-memory ability of these biopolymers need further research, the authors of both studies suggest a similar mechanism as explained for conventional SMPs, where the animal hair (wool)/feathers

Biological materials

Biopolymer-based hybrids

Figure 6. Shape-memory effect in biopolymers and biopolymer-based materials. (a) SME of a peacock's tail feather (upper part), and the two components of the feather rachis (foam and cortex in the lower part), triggered by aqueous environments.⁶⁸ (b) Water-triggered SME of animal hairs.⁶⁹ (c) Gelatin/PAM hydrogel returning to its original shape when induced with temperature or salt concentration.⁷⁶ (d) Thermally induced SME in peptide-derived hydrogels with collagen-like transient nodes.⁷⁸ (e) Coordination-triggered shape-memory process in a hydrogel, including alginate. The system consists of fluorescent alginate–Eu³⁺ complexes acting as temporary switches.⁷⁹ (f) DNA-based shape-memory hydrogels responding to changes in pH.⁸⁰ Panel (a), including the tail feather, is reprinted with permission from ref 68. Copyright 2015 Elsevier. Panel (b), including the animal hair, is adapted with permission from ref 69 under a Creative Commons Attribution 4 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Copyright 2016 Nature Research. Panel (c), including the Gelatin/PAM hydrogel, is republished with permission from ref 76, permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. Copyright 2019 The Royal Society of Chemistry. Panel (d), including peptide-derived hydrogels, is adapted with permission from ref 78. Copyright 2011 American Chemical Society. Panel (e), including alginate hydrogels, is adapted with permission from ref 79. Copyright 2018 American Chemical Society. Panel (f), including DNA-based hydrogels, is adapted with permission from ref 80. Copyright 2014 Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim.

could be fixed to a defined shape permanently by a hybrid structure network. The structural model consists of (i) hydrogen bonds (single-switch) and (ii) twin-netpoints based

on crystalline regions, formed by keratin (α - or β -keratin for hair or feathers, respectively), and disulfide cross-links of cysteine residues that are insensitive to external stimuli.^{68,69}

For instance, the existing hydrogen bonds in hairs and feathers are removed from their original position through hydration (hydrogen bonds are formed between chain residues and water molecules), leaving only chemical and crystalline netpoints to support the polymer structure (Figure 6a). This results in the hair with a lateral swelling and enhanced flexibility of polypeptide chains. Furthermore, the hair can be given any temporary shape that can be fixed by a drying process, where hydrogen bonds can be distorted away from their lowest energy configuration to form temporary hydrogen bonds that lock in the deformed shape. Upon the addition of water, the netpoints relax again into the original shape. For feathers, the innate shape was almost fully recovered after severe deformation by a short hydration step (within 1 min).⁶⁸

The SME of wool materials is attracting considerable attention in the field of smart textiles, and current research in this area suggests that a stronger and higher number of netpoints in the hair would give rise to the better water-sensitive SME (Figure 6b).⁶⁹ This could be taken into consideration when similar synthetic designs are intended. Interestingly, keratin fibers have been reported to respond to various environmental stimuli, such as water, heat, coupled heat–water, UV radiation, and redox agents. This ability offers a high potential for developing an “all-in-one” SMP with multistimuli responsiveness.⁷⁰

A fascinating demonstration of smart polymers in nature is the dragline silk, which shows the most remarkable combination of strength and extensibility, outperforming the best synthetic fibers.⁷¹ Two interesting features related to shape-memory can be highlighted in this material. First, the threads possess a torsional dampening behavior, which causes a hanging spider to hardly ever twist. When a thread from the spider *Araneus diadematus* is twisted, it does not oscillate around the new position, but instead, it slowly returns to its initial position, the “memorized shape”, without any external stimulus. This behavior is due to its high damping coefficient and can be compared to a synthetic thread of “shape-memorizing” nickel–titanium alloy (Nitinol), which is widely used in industry; however, the latter needs to be heated to 90 °C to return to its original shape.⁷² The second feature of spider silk that relates to this Perspective is its water switchable shape-memory capability or capability to undergo supercontraction.⁷³

Supercontraction refers to the large shrinkage of spider silk when immersed in water or subjected to a critical humidity, which is also reversible. The molecular structure conforms to the same pattern explained above and for SMPs. In silk, netpoints are β -sheet crystals, while collective hydrogen bonding among protein chains in amorphous regions fixed the temporary shape (overstretched thread caused by spider's movement). The silk supercontracts to its original shape when the relative humidity of the air changes from dry (0.4%) to wet (90%). Harvesting silks directly from spiders is complex, being necessary to develop engineered fibers inspired by its structure. Shape-memory polyurethane fibers were found to possess high damping ability and, at the same time, have a fairly high strength and toughness. In addition, the polymer fibers could be programmed to induce a SME and to enhance the damping properties, achieving supercontraction upon heating, similar to moisture triggered spider silk.⁷⁴ Biological materials possess

advantages, but understanding the complex hierarchical structure of natural materials remains a challenge; nevertheless, they are and will continue to be models for the development of new types of high-performance engineering materials. Many efforts have been made to combine the special characteristics of biological and synthetic materials by developing hybrid materials, in which the formation of strong and desirable netpoints, the improvement of shape-memory performance, and a better shape recovery ability are possible.

Examples of shape-memory behavior in hybrid materials obtained from biopolymers are depicted in Figure 6. Natural gelatin is a representative derivative protein of collagen, it possesses distinctive biocompatibility and has been widely used for the fabrication of shape-memory hydrogels.^{75–77} With an increase in temperature, gelatin exhibits a reversible coil to triple helix transformations and a decrease of mechanical properties. Gelatin-based hydrogels fixed into a U-shape by cooling to 0 °C could recover its original rod-shape within 5 s after immersing in a water bath at 90 °C. Interestingly, a salt induced SME was furthermore achieved by fixing the hydrogel temporary bent shape in (NH₄)₂SO₄ and sequentially placing it in deionized water to remove the salts. The initial shape was recovered within 120 min (Figure 6c).⁷⁶ A thermally induced SME was achieved in biodegradable recombinant telechelic polypeptides coupled with collagen-like end blocks and a random coil-like middle block. The end blocks consist of nine consecutive Pro-Gly-Pro triplets that formed collagen-like triple helices upon cooling. A lightly, chemically cross-linked polymer network was first obtained by the interaction of lysine residues in the random coil using glutaraldehyde (programmed shape). The hydrogel was then stretched up to 200% and fixed in a temporary shape by cooling down to induce the collagen-like assembly into physical nodes (triple helices). Once the material was exposed to a temperature above which the triple helices melt (~45 °C), it returned to its original shape (Figure 6d).⁷⁸

In addition, a successful example of real-time in situ investigation of the dynamic metal coordination-triggered shape-memory process in a polysaccharides containing hydrogel has been demonstrated.⁷⁹ Here, a system was designed where fluorescent alginate–Eu³⁺ complexes act as temporary switches, introduced into a chemically cross-linked poly-(dimethylacrylamide) (PDMAA) network (permanent hard segment) to produce a PDMAA–alginate hydrogel (Figure 6e). This nonfluorescent hydrogel was deformed by external forces and placed into Eu³⁺ ion solution, allowing the lanthanide metal ion to spontaneously diffuse into the hydrogel and bind to alginate, where the temporary shape (fluorescent appearance) could be fixed. The permanent (nonfluorescent) shape was recovered by decomplexation of the Eu³⁺–alginate cross-links in an aqueous NaF solution, while the shape-memory process could be tracked by the red-light emission of Eu³⁺–alginate complexes.

A more intriguing molecule for the design of shape-memory-based biopolymers has been introduced recently.^{80–83} DNA-based shape-memory hydrogels take advantage of DNA motifs/structures such as the pH-driven formation of C-G-C⁺ or T-A-T triplexes (C, cytosine; G, guanine; A, adenine; T, thymine), the pH-induced assembly of cytosine-rich strands into i-motif configurations and the K⁺-stimulated assembly of G-rich strands into G-quadruplexes. These motifs respond to different stimuli cooperatively cross-linking and stabilizing shaped hydrogels. In general, DNA-based shape-memory

hydrogels include two types of DNA as cross-linkers, where one motif can act as the permanent memory and the other as the stimuli-responsive cross-linker that will control the stiffness of the hydrogel. The bridging of acrylamide polymer chains by two nucleic acid functionalities was reported, where one type of bridging unit provided a stimuli-responsive element and the second unit acted as internal “bridging memory” segment, resulting in a reversible and switchable transition between shaped hydrogels and shapeless quasi-liquid states (Figure 6f).⁸⁰ One of the DNA functions included domains with base pair complementarity (duplex units) that led to the cross-linking of the chains. The other nucleic motif, C-rich tethers, cross-linked the chains at pH = 5.0 by i-motif units. The cooperative cross-linking of the chains by the duplex bridging units and the i-motif structure resulted in the formation of a shaped hydrogel in a mold, providing the interactions for retaining the permanent shape of the hydrogel, upon its exclusion from the mold.⁸⁰ Separation of the i-motif units at pH = 8.0 dissolved the hydrogel into a quasi-liquid phase. The residual duplex units provided a memory code in the quasi-liquid allowing the regeneration of the hydrogel shape at pH = 5.0 and the reformation of the i-motif bridges. Based on the same principle, different combination of external stimuli, such as pH, metal ion/ligand, or photonic signals, have been applied to reversibly reconfigure DNA structures.^{81–83} However, despite the immense progress that has been made, materials scientists are still far from matching nature’s ability to engineer smart synthetic polymers, in terms of structure, versatility, and adaptability.

8. FROM HEAT WRAP TO ARTIFICIAL MUSCLES: EXPANDING THE RANGE OF APPLICATIONS

Shape-memory materials are already established in numerous applications such as heat-shrinkable tubes for insulating packaging, protecting and sealing of parts, and within diverse areas such as automobiles and electronics.⁸⁴ They are highly requested as self-deployable structures for space systems, for example, as hinges to actuate solar array deployment, as booms to support the tip payloads in satellites, or as tapes for the deployment of mesh-surface antennae.⁸⁵ In addition, textiles composed of temperature-sensitive fibers have found uses in transdermal therapy where drugs and moisture can be transferred in a controlled manner as an effective means of skin care.⁸⁶ Shape-shifting materials are furthermore considered as expandable implants as required for minimally invasive surgical processes.³⁵ Here, small objects capable of unfolding or expansion after implantation could be utilized to improve the opening of blocked vessels, to repair cardiac valves, or to facilitate wound closure.^{87–89}

While for these applications thermal responsiveness is generally used, the expansion to directed movements controlled by a diversity of environmental signals has enabled the design of polymeric devices, providing multishape effects or a shape-memory actuation capability in more complex multifunctional devices. Here, SMPs have been used for the design of disposable microfluidic devices.^{90,91} Microvalves capable of shape shifts were implemented into a microfluidic system, enabling the on-demand connection or disconnection of two neighboring microchannels. Furthermore, the ability of materials to reversibly change their macroscopic shape make them interesting in the textile industry as self-regulating cloth materials.⁹² Smart breathable textiles enable the temperature-induced permeability of moisture when the sizes of textile

meshes are increased upon heating, as required for sport clothing products. Potential applications in the field of gerontechnology, such as reversible closure systems for shoes or clothes, are also of interest,⁹³ as well as the design of exoskeletons based on SMPAs to support the motion of old people (e.g., by a tendon-driven hand exoskeleton) or for walking to provide more strength.⁹⁴ The lightweight, soft, and flexible, nature of polymeric materials makes them ideal as artificial muscle actuator devices for robotics.⁸ Here, rotating microengines based on shape-memory nanocomposite fibers could be utilized as muscles, which can store mechanical energy and rotate in response to heat.⁹⁵ In this way, a work capacity that is 60 times higher than that of natural muscle tissue could be obtained. Furthermore, strain-programmable artificial muscles based on actuator fibers were designed, which were thermally and optically controllable. These actuators were able to lift more than 650 times their own weight.⁹⁶ Another example was presented with a sheath-run electrochemical muscle generating an average contractile power, which is 40 times higher than that for a human muscle.⁹⁷ A promising approach has been demonstrated based on the exchange of pneumatic controlling units for reversible SMPAs, which have already demonstrated behavioral complexity and geometric versatility of macroscopic motion. The refinement and development of additive manufacturing technologies has been used in combination with shape-memory technology to create architected intricate SMPA devices. As an example, objects could be grabbed and released by a shape-memory microgripper (e.g., pick up of a bead on a substrate or removal of cells from tissue) in response to temperature or chemical treatment.^{98,99}

Further technological challenges for smart actuators include the improvement of geometric complexity, adjustment of motion kinetics, control of shape shifting forces, and the introduction of reversibility induced by temperature-independent signals. In addition, control methods for generated artificial systems are an area of intense interest, for example, by integrated computers, amplifiers, converters, and transmitters. Finally, the ultimate goal would be the creation of a fully autonomous system, which will receive energy by the environment, will exhibit locomotion, for example, by growth, and will be capable of self-repair.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The input–function–output relationship is the key toward (multi)functional biomaterials with shape programmable (one-way) shape shifts and reversible actuation. Here, an environmental change acts as an input signal and the output takes the form of a (multi)SME. We make the important distinction that the initiation of the actuation function is not simply triggered by an inductive stimulus as with a conventional SME but, instead, is directly controlled by the applied input signal.

When a polymeric device provides more than one material function, the function–function relationship has to be considered and different challenges have to be addressed for orthogonal functions (independent material functions) or sequentially coupled functions (functions are linked by a domino effect). The creation of independent functions within a single complex material system free from interference and crosstalk has to be taken into account for multifunctional materials with orthogonal functions. Contrary to this, in case of sequentially coupled functions, the output intensity of the first

function should be compatible with the input range of the second.

Polymeric materials possessing a shape-memory function can identify their environment and respond to one or more external stimuli. The choice of input signal is no longer limited to heat responsive materials; developments in synthetic polymer chemistry have led to the incorporation of a diverse range of sensitive molecular switches and were closely followed by macroscopic shape shifts induced by a wide variety of stimuli. By incorporating hybrid materials that function as signal converters into polymeric matrices, the incident stimulus can be translated into information readable by the material system. Inductive heating can be generated by utilizing graphene oxide, carbon nanotubes, or iron oxide nanoparticles to convert NIR light, electric, or magnetic fields.

Another conceptual approach is based on the integration of a transmitter into a polymeric shape-memory material. Such a transmitter is capable of controlling the spatial application of incident radiation, transmitting it to the wider material. This has been demonstrated by an architected shape-memory function integration where the combination of a microporous geometry and ultrasonic cavitation based mechanical force induced the disassociation of coordination bonds and, subsequently, the macroscopic directed movement of polymeric materials.

Fabricating new materials that respond to their external environment requires creative molecular design. Here, principles from nature can be inspiring. Although great advances have been made for stimuli-responsive materials, coupling a SME with complex biological environments remains a significant challenge. As the next generation of SMPs, polymeric actuators, are currently limited to changes in temperature as a controlling input signal, future research activities could also concentrate on new material design concepts to address reversible macroscopic movements of shape programmable materials via alternative environmental stimuli.

Biopolymer-based or bioinspired materials are intrinsically highly sensitive to environmental alteration and have been intensively investigated with the aim of matching nature's ability in terms of structure, versatility, and adaptability. Here, the knowledge of the mechanisms of cooperative interactions between biopolymers and their stimuli-sensitivity is necessary to inform design criteria. For example, in keratin-based natural materials a shape-memory behavior that utilizes water as an input signal could be observed, whereby temporary hydrogen bonds able to fix a temporary shape underwent rearrangement to recover their original position upon water treatment. Directed movement harnessing hydrogen bond alteration could also be transferred to gelatin-based hybrid materials, enabling a thermal- and salt-induced shape shift according to a released hydrogen bond based tertiary structure. Furthermore, metal coordination based shape-memory processes in hydrogels including polysaccharides or pH- and ligand-sensitive DNA-based materials have been demonstrated. Despite the immense progress in this field, material research is still far away from mimicking the mechanical versatility within the natural world.

The diversity and complexity of methods within nature to generate environmentally responsive shape change are illustrated within the plant kingdom. Plants are reliant on external information from their surroundings to successfully perform essential functions like reproduction, defense, or

nutrition. While polymeric materials have successfully generated movement directed by system architecture, implementing a directional response to incoming stimulation like that observed in nastic plant motion has proved difficult. The challenges of future scientific efforts in the field of shape programmable materials should concentrate on the design of new approaches that enable a directional response to an incident signal, mimicking the tropistic movement realized by plants and greatly enhancing the potential environmental response of the material.

The design of functional materials is driven by challenges from existing and emergent applications, for self-regulating cloth materials, sensing devices, advanced therapies, drug delivery, implant materials, and for robotics. Hence, the geometric complexity, regulation of shape-shifting kinetics, and generated force, as well as the sensitivity of SMPAs toward a broad range of environmental signals, have to be considered and further explored. By incorporating design concepts from the natural world and integrating material components that act as amplifiers, converters, and transmitters, artificial systems can be controlled autonomously and efficiently.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: andreas.lendlein@hzg.de.

ORCID

Andreas Lendlein: [0000-0003-4126-4670](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4126-4670)

Oliver E. C. Gould: [0000-0002-8034-5724](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8034-5724)

Author Contributions

A.L. conceptualized the article. A.L., M.B., N.A.T., and O.E.C.G. wrote and revised the article.

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Notes

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): A.L. is an inventor of patents and patent application in the field of shape-memory polymers.

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